

Dynamic Drone Mesh Networks for Scalable Quantum Key Distribution in Challenging Environments

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Abstract: Providing secure and scalable cryptographic key distribution in dynamic, infrastructure-less environments remains a major challenge. This work investigates the feasibility and performance of dynamic drone-based mesh networks for Quantum Key Distribution (QKD). A detailed Python-based simulation model was developed, incorporating realistic quantum and classical communication channels, multiple drone mobility strategies, key management mechanisms (including revocation), and simulated adversarial conditions such as jamming and interception. The objectives were to model dynamic environments, evaluate key distribution efficiency, and analyze the influence of configuration and adversarial factors on key availability. Results show that adversarial attacks substantially reduce key availability, emphasizing the need for robust security and adaptive key management. Directed mobility strategies demonstrated improved distribution efficiency compared to random movement. Overall, the findings indicate that dynamic drone mesh networks hold strong potential for scalable QKD deployment in challenging, mobile environments, though performance and resilience strongly depend on network configuration, link quality, and mitigation strategies.

Keywords: Quantum Key Distribution, Drone Networks, Mesh Networks, Mobile Robots, Dynamic Environments, Network Simulation, Key Management, Network Security.

1. INTRODUCTION

Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) represents one of the applications of quantum information, offering a method to establish secret keys whose security is based on principles of quantum mechanics, making it immune to future cryptanalytic attacks, even by advanced quantum computers [Lo, Curty & Tamaki, 2014; Xu, Ma, Zhang, Lo & Pan, 2020]. Despite the advances achieved in controlled laboratory environments and in fixed links (optical fiber or static free space), the implementation of robust global or mobile quantum networks faces substantial practical challenges. These include inherent channel losses, detector errors, temporal synchronization limitations, and, crucially, the dynamic effects of environmental noise, orientation, and vibrations on mobile platforms [Diamanti, Lo, Qi & Yuan, 2016; Xue, Chen, Wang, Yin, Shi & Han, 2021].

The deployment of QKD solutions in dynamic, infrastructure-less environments, such as disaster zones or military scenarios, requires architectures that combine mobility with the ability to retransmit quantum keys securely and scalably. Satellite QKD systems have demonstrated the feasibility of large-scale links; however, they often rely on trusted relays and robust terrestrial infrastructure, which

limits their applicability in mobile or rapid deployment scenarios [Chen et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2018].

This study addresses these limitations by investigating the feasibility and performance of a dynamic mesh network based on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs or drones) for QKD key distribution. A detailed simulation model was developed in Python to evaluate the efficiency of key distribution, analyze mobility strategies, implement key management mechanisms, and measure the system's resilience against adverse conditions, such as jamming and interception. The simulation focused on small-scale scenarios

—drones and robots—, thus addressing the critical "last-mile" mobile phase of quantum networks, where Size, Weight, and Power (SWaP) constraints are determinant. The results show that, although the drone mesh architecture has strong potential for scalable QKD deployment in complex environments, its performance and resilience intrinsically depend on the network configuration, the quality of the physical links, and the adoption of adaptive security and mitigation strategies.

2. METHODOLOGY

A simulation-based approach was adopted to evaluate the performance of a dynamic drone mesh network aimed at scalable key distribution using Quantum Key Distribution (QKD). The simulation environment was represented as a three-dimensional grid with defined spatial boundaries, allowing for a realistic modeling of the operational space in field scenarios.

2.1 System Entities

The simulation included three types of entities:

1. **Robots:** Mobile entities that require cryptographic keys. They are initialized at random positions on the ground plane of the grid ($z=0$) and have a buffer (*buffer_size*) to store received keys with a defined lifetime (*key_duration*) in simulation steps. Robots are capable of recording the step in which keys are received to track delivery rates.
2. **Stations:** Static entities (optional, used to provide spatial context or reference points) with a defined communication range (*range_*). Each station possessed a defined classical communication range but did not actively participate in key distribution.
3. **Drones:** Mobile entities that operate as fundamental transport and relay nodes in the quantum network. They are capable of establishing point-to-point Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) links with other neighboring drones, allowing for the generation and secure exchange of cryptographic material. For the management of these keys, each drone is provided with an internal buffer (*capacity*), which allows it to store keys received from other nodes, thus facilitating the multi-hop propagation of the quantum key. Once the keys are stored, drones have the additional function of delivering these keys to robots within their classical communication range (*range_*), serving as the final bridge to provide quantum cryptography to users on the ground.

2.2 Drone Mobility Strategies

The operational efficacy of the mobile key distribution network is critically dependent on the decision-making process governing drone movement. To comprehensively assess the system's performance, drone mobility is meticulously simulated using a set of distinct and evaluative strategies, collectively referred to as the *movement_strategy* parameter. These strategies are designed to represent a spectrum of movement philosophies, from purely exploratory to highly directed and mission-focused.

The strategies implemented include:

- **Random Movement:** Drones move with no external

influence or goal, simulating simple exploration or a baseline behavior where environmental knowledge is minimal.

- **Directed Movement towards the Nearest Robot:** Drones actively seek the closest robot, prioritizing the immediate replenishment of keys to the nearest consumer. This is a greedy approach focused on minimizing key-delivery latency.
- **Directed Movement towards Key-Scarce Areas:** Drones prioritize navigation towards regions identified as having a critically low current number of active and valid keys. This sophisticated strategy aims to optimize key distribution efficiency across the entire network, preventing localized key shortages.

Regardless of the chosen strategy, the drone's movement speed is standardized. Specifically, the speed is fixed at 1 unit per simulation step on each axis (X, Y, and Z) for the random movement model, and a similar *magnitude* of displacement is maintained for the directed strategies to ensure a fair comparison of the strategic impact alone, isolated from speed variations.

2.3 Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Modeling

The establishment of a secure Quantum Key Distribution link between two adjacent drones is a probabilistic event, which is managed and simulated by an enhanced *KeyManager*. This QKD model is specifically engineered to move beyond idealized scenarios and incorporates multiple realistic quantum channel effects that directly influence the success rate of key generation:

- **Distance-Dependent Photon Loss:** The core physical constraint of QKD over distance is modeled by an attenuation coefficient (*attenuation_coefficient*, measured in dB per distance unit). This loss dictates that the probability of a photon successfully traversing the quantum channel and being transmitted decreases exponentially as the separation between the communicating drones increases.
- **Atmospheric Turbulence:** Environmental factors are captured through a dedicated turbulence factor (*atmospheric_turbulence_strength*). This parameter simulates the scattering and beam wandering caused by atmospheric effects, effectively reducing the stable and effective transmission probability of the quantum signals.
- **Background Noise:** Spurious detections and inherent environmental interference are accounted for by a fixed background noise rate

(*background_noise_rate*). This noise directly contributes to an increased probability of false positive detections at the receiver, raising the raw quantum bit error rate (QBER).

- **Pointing Errors:** The precision of the optical alignment systems is simulated by a standard deviation (*pointing_error_std_dev*). Misalignment due to platform instability or tracking imperfections reduces the coupling efficiency between the drones' transceivers, thereby diminishing the observed signal strength.
- **Protocol Base Error Rate:** An intrinsic, irreducible error floor (*error_rate*) is included to model the inherent imperfections of the QKD protocol implementation itself or the limitations of the physical quantum hardware components.

The overall success of establishing a secure key is determined by a two-stage condition. First, the communicating drones must be within the maximum allowed quantum communication range (*drone_range*). Second, the simulated Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER)—calculated from the sifted bits after factoring in all the aforementioned channel impairments—must fall below a predefined maximum acceptable threshold (*qber_threshold*).

Following successful quantum transmission, a simplified **post-processing** stage, encompassing error correction and privacy amplification, is simulated. The success probability of this stage is functionally dependent on the calculated QBER. A key is ultimately considered **established and secure** only if both the raw QKD process is successful *and* the subsequent post-processing successfully derives a sufficient number of secure bits (currently defined as 64 bits to form an 8-byte cryptographic key).

2.4 Classical Channel for Key Delivery

While quantum channels are used for key generation between drones, the final key delivery from a drone to its target robot is performed using a classical communication channel. This key transfer event is triggered when a robot comes within the defined classical communication range (*drone_range*) of a key-holding drone. The simulation of this classical key transfer is based on a comprehensive channel model that incorporates several key physical layer effects:

- **Path Loss:** The signal power degradation over distance is modeled using a path loss exponent (*classical_path_loss_exponent*), reflecting the environment's attenuation properties.
- **Fading:** Short-term fluctuations in signal strength

are simulated using a simplified statistical model, such as the Rayleigh fading distribution, to represent multipath propagation effects.

- **Noise Floor:** A constant background thermal and electronic noise level (*classical_noise_floor_db*) is maintained, limiting the achievable signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).
- **Transmission Power:** The strength of the transmitted signal is a configurable parameter (*classical_tx_power_dbm*), directly impacting the received power level.

The overall success probability of the classical key transfer is calculated based on the resulting Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), which is derived from the interplay of the transmission power, path loss, fading, and noise floor. Additionally, a baseline probability of interference (*base_interference_prob*) is included. Crucially, the model also supports an adversarial layer: a simulated adversary may attempt to intercept this key transfer within specific, defined geographical or temporal areas, controlled by the *interception_params_adversary* settings.

2.5 Key Management and Security

A robust and flexible key management system was implemented to maintain the integrity and currency of the cryptographic keys distributed throughout the network.

- **Automatic Expiration (TTL):** Every key is created with a defined Time-To-Live (TTL). Keys are automatically considered expired and are systematically removed from the buffers of both drones and robots once their assigned validity duration is exhausted, preventing the continued use of stale or long-lived keys.
- **Revocation Scheme:** To address potential security breaches, a key revocation mechanism was integrated. In the event a specific key is compromised (e.g., through an adversary's successful interception), it can be instantaneously marked as invalid. The system ensures that this compromised key is immediately and reliably purged from all active buffers across the entire network, thereby maintaining the overall system integrity and security posture.

2.6 Evaluation Scenarios

To fully characterize the performance and resilience of the simulated key distribution network, the simulation was executed across a wide array of evaluation scenarios. This

systematic approach involved the methodical variation of key operating and environmental parameters:

- **Network Density:** Varying the number of active drones and robots to test scalability and congestion effects.
- **Environment Size:** Altering the physical dimensions of the simulated operational area.
- **Communication Range:** Adjusting the maximum effective range for both the quantum (QKD) and classical communication links.
- **Robot Buffer Capacity:** Changing the maximum number of keys a robot can store, impacting key-delivery efficiency.
- **Key Validity Duration (TTL):** Modifying the key's Time-To-Live to assess the impact of key refresh rates.
- **QKD Link Quality:** Adjusting parameters like the *attenuation_coefficient* and *atmospheric_turbulence_strength* to simulate varied channel conditions.
- **Classical Channel Conditions:** Modifying the *classical_path_loss_exponent* and *classical_noise_floor_db*.

A critical part of the evaluation involved **Adversarial Scenarios**, which were designed to stress-test the system's security and resilience against real-world threats:

- **Interference (Jamming) on QKD Links:** Simulating active denial-of-service attacks against the quantum channel establishment.
- **Interception during Classical Delivery:** Modeling a successful eavesdropper during the drone-to-robot key transfer.
- **Massive Key Revocation:** Testing the system's ability to recover and re-establish key availability following a system-wide security event requiring the invalidation of a large set of keys.

This comprehensive testing matrix allowed for a robust evaluation of the system's *robustness* against environmental uncertainties, its *resilience* to deliberate attacks, and the overall *effectiveness* of the key distribution and security mechanisms.

2.7 Performance Metrics

The success of the key distribution system was quantified using two primary performance metrics, measured over the course of the simulation:

1. **Average Key Delivery Rate:** This metric tracks the mean number of valid keys successfully transferred from drones to robots per unit of time, reflecting the throughput and efficiency of the distribution process.

2. **Average Number of Active and Valid Keys per Robot:** This metric provides a measure of continuous **key availability** at the consumer (robot) level over time, ensuring that the robots have sufficient secure material for their operations.

Each defined evaluation scenario was run for a fixed duration of **100 time steps**, with performance data systematically recorded at each step. Figure 1 serves as an illustrative example of the kind of results gathered; however, it is important to note that the figure's data is based on a preliminary, less realistic version of the simulation model compared to the advanced scenarios and modeling techniques analyzed in this specific study.

Figure 1: Impact of density and environment size on key availability

The pseudocode describing the main logic of the drone mesh network simulation for Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) is presented below. This algorithm details the iterative steps for environment initialization, entity movement, quantum link establishment, key management and delivery to robots, as well as the simulation of adverse conditions.

FUNCTION Simulate_Mesh_Network(grid_size, steps, params):

 grid ← Initialize_Grid(grid_size, params) // Robots, Drones, Estaciones

 KeyRevocationManager ← Initialize_Key_Manager()

 Metrics ← Initialize_Metrics()

 FOR step ← 0 TO steps - 1 DO

 Simulate_Adversary_Actions(step, grid, params.interception_params_adversary)

 Simulate_Revocation_Event(step, KeyRevocationManager, params.revocation_prob)

```

FOR each drone IN grid.drones DO
    Move_Drone(drone, grid.robots,
params.movement_strategy)

    // Estrategias: aleatoria, dirigida, por densidad de claves

// ----- Fase Cuántica -----

FOR each pair (d1, d2) IN grid.drones DO

    IF distance(d1, d2) ≤ params.drone_qkd_range THEN

        key ← Establish_Key(d1, d2, params)

        IF key ≠ None THEN

            Store_Key_In_Mesh(key, d1, d2)

// ----- Fase Clásica -----

FOR each robot IN grid.robots DO

    FOR each drone IN grid.drones DO

        IF distance(drone, robot) ≤ params.drone_classical_range
THEN

            IF Channel_Success(drone, robot, params) THEN

                key_data ← drone.Derive_And_Provide_Key(robot)

                IF key_data ≠ None THEN

                    robot.Add_Key(key_data, step)

            Update_Key_Buffers(grid.robots, KeyRevocationManager) //
TTL + revocación

            Calculate_Performance_Metrics(step, grid.robots, Metrics)

        END FOR

    RETURN Metrics.results

FUNCTION Establish_Key(e1, e2, params):

    IF Jamming_Check(params) THEN RETURN None

    η_total ← Calculate_Channel_Efficiency(

        distance(e1, e2),

        params.attenuation_coefficient,

        params.atmospheric_turbulence_strength,

        params.pointing_error_std_dev)

```

```

E ← Compute_QBER(η_total,

    params.background_noise_rate,

    params.error_rate)

IF E > params.qber_threshold THEN RETURN None

IF PostProcessing_Success(E) THEN

    R_secure ← Compute_Secure_Bits(E)

    IF R_secure ≥ params.secure_bits_required THEN

        RETURN Generate_Key_Data(R_secure)

    END IF

RETURN None

```

3. RESULTS

Exhaustive simulations were conducted to evaluate the performance of the dynamic QKD drone mesh network under a wide range of operational, environmental, and security conditions. Scenarios systematically varied key parameters such as drone and robot density, environment size, QKD link quality, classical channel conditions, movement strategies, adversarial attacks, and key management events like revocation. Performance was primarily measured by the average number of active and valid keys per robot over time, a metric that directly reflects the network's capacity to keep end entities supplied with usable cryptographic material. The following subsections present the key findings from these detailed simulations.

3.1 Impact of Density and Environment Size

To understand the influence of network scale and the physical environment, scenarios were simulated by varying the density of robots and drones (low, medium, high) and the environment size (small, medium, large). The results obtained, illustrated in Figure 2, clearly demonstrate how these fundamental factors affect key availability over time.

The baseline simulations explored how the density of robots and drones and the size of the environment affect key availability.

Figure 2: Impact of Density and Environment Size

3.2 Impact of QKD Link Quality and Environmental Conditions

The quality of quantum links and the influence of environmental conditions are critical for the success of QKD. Simulations were carried out varying the base error rate of the QKD protocol, the QBER threshold, simulated atmospheric turbulence, and background noise. Figure 3 shows how these variations in link quality and environmental conditions impact the average number of active and valid keys for the robots.

Figure 3: Impact of QKD Link Quality and Environmental Conditions on Key Availability

3.3 Impact of Adversary Attacks

To evaluate the network's robustness against external threats, scenarios with different types of adversary attacks were simulated: jamming on QKD links and interception of key delivery to robots. These scenarios were compared with a baseline without an adversary. Figure 4 shows the impact of these targeted attacks on key availability over time.

Figure 4: Impact of Adversarial Attacks on Key Availability

3.4 Impact of Key Management (Revocation)

Key management is essential for security, particularly the ability to revoke compromised keys. A key revocation event was simulated at a specific step of the simulation and performance was compared with a baseline scenario without revocation, as well as with a revocation scenario with a longer key duration. Figure 5 illustrates the effect of revocation on the average number of active and valid keys.

Figure 5: Impact of Key Revocation on Key Availability

3.5 Impact of Movement Strategies

The way drones move in the dynamic environment directly influences their ability to establish QKD links and meet with robots to deliver keys. Different drone movement strategies were compared: random movement (baseline), movement directed towards the nearest robot, and movement directed towards areas with a low key count. Figure 6 presents the impact of these strategies on key availability for the robots over time.

Figure 6: Impact of Drone Movement Strategies on Key Availability

Beyond the individual impact of parameters, it is crucial to understand how they interact with each other. Scenarios were designed to explore the combination of different factors, such as high density in a large environment with a high error rate, or high interference combined with directed movement strategies or attacks. Figure 7 shows the results of these interaction scenarios, highlighting the complex effects that can arise.

Figure 7: Impact of Parameter Interactions on Key Availability

4. DISCUSSION

The results of the exhaustive simulations provide detailed quantitative evidence on the performance of the dynamic drone mesh network for quantum key distribution (QKD) under different operational, environmental, and security conditions. This section interprets the findings in the context of existing literature and analyzes the specific contribution of the proposed architecture.

4.1 Impact of Operational, Environmental, and Security Factors

The simulations reveal how different physical and network

factors interdependently influence the system's efficiency and reliability. Figure 2 shows that a higher density of drones and robots significantly increases the average number of active keys per robot, especially in smaller environments. This behavior is explained by the higher probability of close encounters, which favor both the establishment of quantum links between drones and the subsequent delivery of classical keys to the robots. However, in large environments, even with relatively high densities, key availability decreases, demonstrating the difficulty of maintaining coverage and connectivity in extensive spaces. These results confirm that proximity and node density are determinants of the efficiency of a mobility-based dynamic QKD network.

The quality of quantum links and environmental conditions also proved to be critical factors for system performance. As observed in Figure 3, the degradation of quantum channels—for example, through an increase in the quantum bit error rate (QBER) or the presence of background noise—reduces the probability of successful key establishment, limiting overall availability. Similarly, interference in the classical channel affects key delivery to the robots, underscoring the need to employ robust QKD technologies, environmental mitigation techniques (such as adaptive optics, if viable at drone operating altitudes), and communication protocols resilient to electromagnetic or physical interference.

Regarding security, Figure 4 shows that adversary attacks, particularly jamming on quantum links and interception of classical key delivery, cause a notable reduction in the number of active keys available. During periods of combined attack, the network shows the most severe and prolonged degradation, highlighting the inherent vulnerability of quantum and classical communications in environments without fixed infrastructure. This behavior emphasizes the importance of designing and implementing active detection and mitigation countermeasures that strengthen both the quantum and classical layers of the system.

The analysis of Figure 5 shows that the implemented key revocation mechanism is effective for quickly eliminating compromised keys and recovering system integrity. However, the speed with which key availability is re-established after a revocation event directly depends on the system's capacity to generate and distribute new secure keys. These results reveal a fundamental trade-off between the key duration—which helps maintain availability—and the potential exposure to a breach.

Finally, the results presented in Figure 6 indicate that mobility strategies have a significant impact on the overall system efficiency. Directed strategies, such as movement

toward nearby robots or toward regions with fewer keys, outperform random movement in most simulated scenarios. This behavior suggests that intelligent mobility can optimize the frequency of successful encounters and, therefore, improve distribution efficiency, constituting a key area for the design of more adaptive dynamic quantum networks.

4.2 Specific Contribution Compared to Previous Studies

QKD research has advanced in fixed links (fiber) and long-range links (satellite). However, the critical gap in the mobile "quantum last mile," especially in dynamic environments without infrastructure, has remained largely unexplored at the network architecture level.

Previous experimental studies have demonstrated the viability of point-to-point QKD links using drones: for example, a Secret Key Rate (SKR) of 8.48 kHz was achieved at 200 m using the BB84 decoy-state protocol. Similarly, theoretical analyses of UAVs as quantum relays have established a maximum channel loss capacity of 26 dB to maintain a viable key rate.

The present study advances this research area by addressing the challenge at the level of a dynamic and scalable mesh network, with the specific contribution of:

Architectural Focus: The work focuses on the long-term performance of a multi-hop (mesh) network where drones act as trusted relays and key managers in 3D, a missing quantum analog in classical mobile communications.

Operational Security Assessment: The practical resilience of the system is quantified against dynamic threats (jamming and interception) and operational failures (revocation), factors that are crucial for field deployment but are often omitted in pure physical link analyses.

Impact of Intelligent Mobility: It is demonstrated that the mobility control layer (directed strategies) is a determining factor for network efficiency, improving key availability compared to random movement (Figure 6).

4.3 Relation to Related Work

The results obtained align with existing literature on mobile ad-hoc networks and drone swarms, where node density, connectivity, and channel quality are determinants of system stability. Likewise, they reinforce the known challenges of free-space QKD, particularly its sensitivity to atmospheric conditions and link geometry. The main contribution of this work lies in the systematic evaluation of these factors in the context of a scalable mesh architecture that distributes keys to

three-dimensional mobile entities, thus addressing an identified research gap in the integration of mobility, security, and scalability in QKD environments.

4.3.1 Comparative Performance Analysis

The value of the proposed architecture is emphasized by a direct comparison between the performance metrics reported in previous studies and those obtained in this work. While most existing approaches focus on physical link efficiency—such as the Secret Key Rate (SKR) or channel loss (e.g., 8.48 kHz at 200m or maximum loss of 26 dB in the works of Conrad et al. (2023) and MDI-QKD/OAM (2024), respectively)—the presented architecture introduces and is evaluated under a more holistic network metric: Key Availability. This metric reflects the sustained capacity for secure exchange in dynamic and three-dimensional environments, a fundamental aspect for real applicability.

In contrast to systems that focus on individual link performance, this simulated mesh network model emphasizes collaborative management and directed mobility. The results show that this multi-hop architecture achieves greater sustained efficiency in key availability (network metric), which translates into better scalability, three-dimensional resilience, and robust support for last-mile scenarios, where point-to-point approaches are insufficient.

4.4 Practical Implications

The findings suggest that dynamic QKD drone mesh networks are technically viable for providing secure key distribution in environments without infrastructure, although their performance depends on careful system design. The interaction between drone mobility, the robustness of quantum and classical channels, dynamic key management, and protection against both quantum and conventional attacks needs to be considered. A balanced integration of these components will allow for the development of more reliable and efficient systems.

4.4 Study Limitations

This study is based on a simulation environment that, although advanced, simplifies various aspects of the real world. The QKD and classical channel models represent idealized approximations of physics and environmental noise. The adversary model is limited and does not cover all possible attack vectors. Likewise, physical constraints such as energy consumption, drone payload capacity, or flight regulations in complex spaces are not included.

Overall, the results demonstrate that dynamic QKD drone

mesh networks possess significant potential for challenging environments, but their effectiveness depends on link quality, resilience to threats, and the implementation of adaptive mobility and management strategies. These findings guide the conclusions and define the main directions for future work.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study explored the viability and performance of dynamic drone mesh networks for scalable Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) in challenging environments using a detailed three-dimensional simulation model. A 3D environment was developed with key-carrying drones and mobile robots, incorporating realistic quantum and classical channel models, differentiated mobility strategies, basic key management mechanisms, and scenarios with adversary attacks. The simulations, executed under various network configurations and operating conditions, provided quantitative information on the factors that determine the effectiveness of this approach.

Overall, the results demonstrate that drone mesh networks represent a promising alternative for enabling QKD in scenarios where fixed infrastructure is impracticable or vulnerable. The analysis confirms that node density, link quality, environmental conditions, key management, and mobility strategies are determining factors in the availability and efficiency of key distribution. Likewise, the simulation of attacks evidenced the need to implement robust countermeasures in both layers—quantum and classical—to maintain security and service continuity.

5.1 Objective Fulfillment

The objectives set in this study were satisfactorily achieved:

1. **Modeling and simulation of the dynamic environment:** A three-dimensional model was developed with realistic representation of drones, robots, and stations, integrating physical models of quantum and classical channels.
2. **Effectiveness evaluation:** Scenarios were designed and executed that systematically varied parameters such as density, environment size, channel quality, and environmental conditions, quantifying performance through key availability metrics.
3. **Analysis of mobility, management, and attacks:** Movement strategies, key revocation, and jamming and interception attacks were studied, obtaining quantitative evidence on their impact on system availability and efficiency.
4. **Global evaluation of the approach:** Empirical results were generated that demonstrate the potential of the

mesh architecture to provide scalable and robust QKD in dynamic environments, while identifying its main limitations.

5.2 Key Findings

The simulations showed that higher drone density and smaller environment size significantly increase key availability. QKD link quality and environmental conditions directly influence the transmission success rate, while adversary attacks severely reduce the number of active keys. Revocation was established as an essential control mechanism, and directed mobility strategies showed a consistent improvement in distribution efficiency. These results strengthen the understanding of the dynamics and challenges of mobile QKD networks in complex three-dimensional environments.

5.3 Future Work

Based on the findings and recognizing the limitations of the current model, several priority lines of research are identified:

1. **Advanced modeling and experimental validation:** Integrate more detailed physical models of QKD protocols (e.g., BB84, E91) and channel effects (depolarization, fiber-to-space coupling), along with experimental validation using real drone platforms in controlled environments.
2. **Optimization of control, mobility, and key assignment:** Develop cooperative route planning and distributed drone control algorithms that optimize key delivery according to the network status and the dynamic needs of the receivers.
3. **Resilient network protocols and key management:** Design adaptive routing protocols and decentralized key management with mutual authentication, secure revocation, and deletion mechanisms on compromised drones.
4. **Formal security evaluation and attack mitigation:** Extend the analysis to advanced adversaries, including malicious drones or impersonation attacks, and implement anti-jamming and real-time intrusion detection strategies.
5. **Hardware considerations and practical deployment:** Incorporate real constraints on weight, energy, bandwidth, and air regulation, as well as explore hybrid architectures that combine fixed stations with mobile drones to improve coverage and resilience.

By addressing these areas, future research can advance toward the practical implementation of efficient, secure, and scalable QKD drone mesh networks, contributing to the development of quantum-safe communication infrastructures in dynamic real-world environments.

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